

“A study to assess the effectiveness of positioning technique on oxygenation status among COPD patients in NMCH, Rohtas, Bihar”

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Abstract—Background: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is progressive lung disease characterized by airflow limitation, breathlessness, and impaired oxygenation. It significantly affects the quality of life and increases the risk of morbidity and mortality. Effective management of COPD includes both pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions. Among these, positioning techniques are simple, low-cost nursing interventions that can improve lung expansion, reduce dyspnea, and enhance oxygen saturation. Objective: The main objective of this study was to assess the effectiveness of positioning technique on oxygenation status—as measured by arterial oxygen saturation (SpO₂), partial pressure of oxygen (PaO₂)

Method: A quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design was employed among 60 COPD patients selected through purposive sampling. Baseline oxygenation parameters were recorded. A structured positioning protocol was implemented every 2 hours over a 72-hour period. Result: The findings of the study indicated that the mean post-test oxygen saturation level was significantly higher than the mean pre-test level. This demonstrates that positioning techniques had a positive effect on improving oxygenation among COPD patients. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between pre-test and post-test values, confirming the effectiveness of the intervention.

Conclusion: The study concludes that positioning techniques are effective in improving oxygenation status among COPD patients. These techniques are simple, cost-effective, and non-invasive, making them highly suitable for routine nursing practice. Incorporating proper positioning into standard patient care can enhance respiratory function, reduce complications, and improve overall patient outcomes in COPD management.

Index Terms— COPD, Oxygenation saturation Monitoring, Patient Positioning, Fowler's position.

Keyword - COPD, Positioning technique, Oxygenation technique, NMCH, Rohtas Bihar, Medical Health Nursing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a progressive and debilitating respiratory disorder characterized by persistent airflow limitation, chronic inflammation of the airways, and impaired gas exchange. It is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide and significantly affects the physical, psychological, and social well-being of individuals. COPD is commonly associated with risk factors such as smoking, air pollution, occupational exposure to dust and chemicals, and recurrent respiratory infections. Census of COPD (World) *Global Scenario*: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease is a major public health problem worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, COPD is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality globally. It is estimated that: Around 390million people are affected worldwide Problem Statement: A study to assess the effectiveness of the positioning technique on oxygenation status among COPD patient in NMCH, Rohtas, Bihar.

Aim: to assess the effectiveness of positioning technique on oxygenation status—as measured by arterial oxygen saturation (SpO₂), partial pressure of oxygen (PaO₂). Objective: To assess the pre test level of oxygenation status among patients.

To assess the post test level of oxygenation status among patients.

To determine the effectiveness of positioning techniques on oxygenation status among patients

To associate the post-test level of oxygenation status with socio demographic variables among patients

Hypothesis :

H1 - There is a significant differences between the pre-test and post test level of oxygenation status among COPD patients admitted at NMCH, Bihar. H2 - There will be significant association between post level of oxygenation status with socio demographic variables among patients admitted at NMCH, Rohtas, Bihar.

Assumptions:

- COPD patients included in the study will cooperate and actively participate during the positioning intervention.
- Positioning techniques are assumed to have a potential physiological effect on lung expansion and oxygenation status
- The selected tools (pulse oximeter/ABG reports/respiratory assessment scale) will provide accurate and reliable measurements of oxygenation status.
- The patients' clinical condition will remain relatively stable during the period of data collection.
- Nurses or researchers implementing the positioning techniques will follow standardized procedures throughout the study
- Participants will provide honest responses regarding their symptoms and comfort levels if subjective scales are used.

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- The sample selected will be representative of COPD patients admitted in NMCH, Rohtas, Bihar.

Delimitation:

- The research will focus only on selected positioning techniques (such as semi-Fowler's, Fowler's, or prone/lateral as per protocol).
- The study is to assess only oxygenation status parameters (e.g., SpO₂ level, respiratory rate, or ABG if applicable).
- The research is to be confined to hospital settings and not extended to home-based or community COPD patients.

II. METHODOLOGY

Aspect	Details
Research Approach	Quantitative
Research Design	Quasi-Experimental one group Pre-test post test
Setting	Hospital (NMCH, jamuhar, Rohtas)
Population	Adults COPD patient aged of about (21-60 years) admitted in Medicine & ICU
Sample Size	60
Sampling Technique	Non-probability convenience sampling
Analysis	SPSS: descriptive, t-test, χ^2 ($p < 0.05$)

Table 1.1 Brief Description About Research Methodology

Sampling Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- COPD patients aged below 21- 60 years diagnosed as per GOLD criteria
- Baseline SpO₂ between 75-94% on room air

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- Able to understand and follow instructions
- Able to maintain sitting position for 30minutes
- Willing to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with acute COPD exacerbation
- Patients with severe orthopedic deformities
- Patients with recent thoracic/abdominal surgery
- Critically ill patients

Description of tools

Section A: Demographic and Clinical Data - Age, gender, area of living, reigion, COPD duration, smoking history, co-morbidities, current medications (08 items)

Section B: Observation Record - SpO2 readings (pretest and post test), positioning duration, any adverse events. Pulse Oximeter: Nonin WristOx2 3150 model with finger probe for accurate SpO2 measurement and Scoring And Interpretation.

SpO2 Category	Range
Mild	90-94%
Moderate	75-89%
Severe	<75%

Table 1.2 Scoring And Interpretation

Method of Data Collection

Daily screening of ward admissions for eligible COPD patients, Informed consent and baseline data collection, Pretest SpO2 measurement in supine position (3 readings, average taken), Intervention: Tripod positioning - patient sits leaning forward 45° on bedside table with arms supported on pillow for 30 minutes, Posttest SpO2 measurement in same position (3 readings, average taken) Data recorded in structured proforma.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

III. RESULT

The result of the study is organized into following sections,

Section I: description of demographic variables, there are total 39 male patients and 21 female patients. This table shows, there are 2 patients of below 21 years, 15 patients of 21-32 years, 20 patients of 33-46 years and 23 patients of 47-60 years, there are 19 patients comes under rural area & 41 patients comes under urban area, 70% patients are belongs to Hindu religion, 28.3% belongs to Muslim religion and 1.67% comes to other religion (Christian, Jain, Sikh etc), Most patients fall in the 4-7 years category, which has the highest frequency (25 cases, 41.6%), more than 7 years of COPD (20 cases, 33.3%), The 1-3 years group has a moderate number of patients (14 cases, 23.3%), while less than 1 year has the lowest frequency (1 case, 1.67%). The highest proportion (60%) of individuals have been smoking for 6-10 years, about 23.3% have been smoking for more than 10 years, about 16.6% of participants have a smoking history of 1-5 years, No participants (0%) reported smoking for less than 1 year. the largest proportion is Hypertension, accounting for 56.6%, Diabetes Mellitus contributes 18.3%, while Others make up 16.6% of the cases. The least common condition is Psychological Problem, comprising only 8.3%,

Section II - Patient oxygenation status - SpO₂ reading (pre-test & post test) the oxygenation saturation by without giving position in pre-test 25% are under severe criteria, 48.3% are under moderate criteria, and 26.6% are under mild criteria, after given the position (Semi - fowlers) the post-test is 90% are in mild criteria, 10% are in moderate criteria, and no any result in severe criteria.

Section III - Effectiveness of positioning technique on oxygenation status among COPD patients As per pre-test and post-test pre and post positioning techniuqe. The mean post-test SpO₂score (2.90 ±0.30) was higher than the pre-test score (2.02 ± 0.72). The calculated t-value was 8.74, which was statistically highly significant at p < 0.0001. The study concluded that H1 (research hypothesis) is accepted.

Section IV - association with demographical variables Gender Male patients had higher mild oxygenation (81.67%) compared to females (8.33%). Moderate level was also slightly higher in males. No severe cases in any gender. Interpretation : There is no significant association between gender and oxygenation status. Age Most patients were in 47–60 years (33.33%) and 33–46 years (30%) groups with mild oxygenation. Very few moderate cases and no severe cases. Interpretation: There is no significant association between age and oxygenation status. Religion Majority were Hindu (63.33%), followed by Muslim (25%). Oxygenation levels were mostly mild across all groups. Interpretation: There is no significant association between religion and oxygenation status. Area (Rural/Urban) Urban patients showed higher mild oxygenation (60%) than rural (25%). Moderate cases were few in both groups. Interpretation: There is no significant association between area of residence and oxygenation status. There is significant effectiveness of Positioning technique on the level of oxygenation saturation among COPD patients. There is no significant association of level of oxygenation status among COPD patients with their socio-demographical variables.

IV. DISCUSSION

The detailed discussion of the findings based on the stated objectives of the study. The study was conducted among 60 patients in NMCH, Rohtas, Bihar, to evaluate the effectiveness in COPD patients.

1. The present study revealed that, prior to the implementation of positioning techniques, most of COPD patients had 15 (25%) are under severe criteria, 29 (48.3%) are under moderate criteria, and 16 (26.6%) are under mild criteria compromised oxygenation status. 2. Post-intervention findings showed a significant improvement in oxygenation status among COPD patients after applying positioning techniques. Oxygen saturation levels increased 54 (90%) are in mild criteria, 06 (10%) are in moderate criteria, and no any result in severe criteria noticeably after positioning interventions such as semi-Fowler's position. This improvement can be attributed to better lung expansion, improved diaphragmatic movement, enhanced secretion clearance, and improved ventilation-perfusion matching. 3. The study revealed that the mean post-test SpO₂ score (2.90 ± 0.30) was higher than the pre-test score (2.02 ± 0.72). The comparison between pre-test and post-test oxygenation scores clearly indicated that positioning techniques were effective in improving oxygenation status. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between pre-intervention and post-intervention values. Analysis of pre-test and post-test oxygenation status among COPD patient. The mean score is 2.02 (S.D= 0.72) in pretest to 2.90 (S.D = 0.30) in post-test. The t test computed between the pre-test and post-test SpO₂ status (t=8.74). The chi-square of the number of gender : 2.24 The chi-square of the number of age : 1.73 The chi - square of the number of the religion : 0.19 The chi-square of the number of residence: 1.78 The chi - square of the number of COPD duration : 13.3 The chi - square of the number of Smoking history : 6.31 The chi - square of the number of co-morbid conditions : 9.98.

Nursing Implications

Nursing Practice

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- Nurses can incorporate positioning techniques (such as semi-Fowler's positions) as a routine part of care for COPD patients to improve oxygenation.
- It emphasizes the importance of regular monitoring of oxygen saturation (SpO₂) during patient positioning.
- Encourages nurses to provide individualized care based on patient comfort and respiratory status.

Nursing Education

- The findings can be included in nursing curriculum to enhance knowledge regarding non-pharmacological management of COPD.
- Nursing students can be trained in correct positioning techniques and their physiological benefits.
- Promotes evidence-based learning and practice among nursing professionals.

Nursing Administration

- Nurse administrators can develop protocols and guidelines for positioning techniques in respiratory care units.
- Ensures availability of supportive devices like pillows and adjustable beds for proper positioning.
- Encourages in-service education and training programs for staff nurses.

Nursing Research

- The study provides a base for further research on positioning techniques in different respiratory conditions.
- Encourages larger-scale studies with diverse populations for better generalization.
- Suggests exploring long-term effects of positioning on oxygenation and patient outcomes

Limitation:-

- Smaller sample size.
- Short duration of the study.
- Lack of higher analysis.
- Homogenous population

Recommendation

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- Positioning techniques such as upright sitting, forward-leaning (orthopneic), and lateral positions should be routinely used in COPD patient care.
- Nurses should prioritize semi-Fowler's and high-Fowler's positions to improve oxygenation and reduce dyspnea.
- Continuous monitoring of SpO₂, respiratory rate, and comfort level should be done after positioning
- Demonstrations and return demonstrations should be included to ensure proper technique.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study supports that proper positioning techniques significantly improve oxygenation status among COPD patients and should be routinely incorporated into patient care protocols to enhance clinical outcomes and quality of life. The study demonstrated that patients who received appropriate positioning interventions, such as semi-Fowler's positions, showed noticeable improvement in oxygen saturation levels compared to their pre-intervention status. These positions help in enhancing lung expansion, reducing the work of breathing, and promoting better ventilation-perfusion matching. Objectives of the study is to assess the pre-test level of oxygenation status among patients, To assess the post test level of oxygenation status among patients admitted at NMCH, To determine the effectiveness of positioning techniques on oxygenation status among patients admitted at NMCH, and To associate the post-test level of oxygenation status with socio demographic variables among patients admitted at NMCH.

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